

NOVEL CHARACTERISATION TECHNIQUE FOR ASSESSMENT OF DAMAGE TO PLATES BY BALLISTIC IMPACT

K. Kandan¹, B.P. Russell^{1*}, V.S. Deshpande¹ and N.A. Fleck¹

¹ Department of Engineering, Cambridge University, U.K

* Corresponding author (bpr23@cam.ac.uk)

Keywords: *composite, damage, ballistic loading, multi-impact*

1 Introduction

A novel characterisation technique is proposed for the assessment of ballistic damage of plates and the residual capacity of such plates to sustain further ballistic loading. Damage mechanisms in composites are complex and numerous [1,2] and is generally assessed by either visual techniques such as microscopy [3] or 3D X-ray tomography or residual property tests where for example, the knock-down in compressive strength of an impacted specimen is compared with an undamaged one [4,5].

The technique presented here considers the knock-down in penetration velocity of a projectile on a plate that has been previously hit by an identical projectile at the same position. Multi-hit scenarios are of interests in both military and civilian applications, for example, bird strike on the fuselage of commercial composite airliners, containment of aircraft engine blade fragments, munitions rounds and blast entrained debris. Here it is of interest to know the residual resistance to a subsequent impact that might arise from collision with a flock of birds.

2 A novel characterisation technique

The degradation characteristic of a plate subjected to a non-penetrating ballistic event can be mapped out in the following way. A projectile is impacted on to a plate target at some velocity V_1 such that $V_1 < V_{BL}$, where V_{BL} is the ballistic limit of the plate. A second projectile is launched at a velocity V_2 and impacted at the *same location* on the plate, and the survival or failure status of the plate is noted (Fig. 1a). In this way, for each V_1 , a series of tests at different values of V_2 are conducted such that the boundary between survival and failure is established

(Fig. 1b). These points can be charted in $V_1 - V_2$ space, and the resultant trajectory shows the susceptibility of a particular plate to ballistic damage.

2.1 The form of the limit-boundary

Of this limit-boundary two coordinates are known *a priori*, the location where the ballistic limit is reached immediately ($V_1 = V_{BL}$ and $V_2 = 0$) and lying on the other axis, the point assuming a zero velocity initial impact ($V_1 = 0$ and $V_2 = V_{BL}$).

Of course, the equation governing all locations between these points, $V_2 = f(V_1)$, will be some a function of the material properties and plate geometry, and is likely to exhibit a non-linear form as mechanistic changes might well be assume to occur at certain transition velocities. A couple of ‘model’ limit-boundaries can be plotted on the chart describing armour plates showing idealised interaction behaviours. The simplest limit-line shows a non-interaction effect. In this case, the equation of the line is independent of V_1 and $V_2 = V_{BL}$ for all values of V_1 , up to V_{BL} (Fig. 1c). In a material which is elastic up to failure, this may be expected to be the characteristic for such a plate. Another limit-boundary might be defined from the sum of the kinetic energies of the two impacts (Fig. 1c), i.e.

$$V_2 = (V_{BL}^2 - V_1^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

This characteristic would be typical of a material that showed large ductility to failure, where the

kinetic energy of the projectile was absorbed primarily through plastic deformation of the plate.

2.2 Definition of a scalar parameter

Whilst this method shows clearly the damage characteristics of a plate, it does not lend itself to an easy comparison between many such plates, due to the potentially non-linear boundary between the survival and failure regions. Many instances in which a knowledge of the multi-impact behavior of a plate is desirable concern events where the first and second impact are of similar mass and velocity. For such instances, it can be helpful to define a scalar quantity that will give a measure of the multi-impact response. A line of slope one in $V_1 - V_2$ space, i.e. where $V_1 = V_2$, will intersect with the survival-failure limit-boundary at a velocity where the second projectile is on the cusp of failing the plate (Fig.1d). This double equal velocity penetration limit not becomes the critical design value, rather than the undamaged ballistic limit, for design scenarios where multi-impact performance is critical.

3 Experimental

Carbon fibre/epoxy composite plates with a lay-up $[0/90]_8$ and 304 stainless steel plates both of the same areal mass were impacted with spherical steel projectiles fired from a gas gun, Fig. 2. Square plates measuring 150 mm along the length were through-holed and clamped with an annular ring such that the unsupported diameter was 100 mm. The area density was kept constant at 5.7 kg m^{-2} by using plates of thickness 3.5 and 0.71 mm for the composite and stainless steel respectively. The projectile used was a spherical steel ball bearing measuring 12.7 mm in diameter and weighing 8.6 g. The velocity range used for the experiments was 25 to 200 ms^{-1} .

High speed photography was used to capture the deformation at both the front and back faces of the plates. A Phantom v12 camera (Vision Research, NJ, USA) was used with a inter-frame time of $10 \mu\text{s}$ and an exposure time of $1 \mu\text{s}$.

4 Results + Discussion

4.1 Boundary-limit characteristics

By making use of the methodology detailed in Section 2, maps of $V_1 - V_2$ space were plotted for

both the carbon fibre composite and stainless steel plate specimens (Fig. 3). The characteristics for these two plates are quite distinct.

4.1.1 Stainless steel specimens

These plates show a gradual deterioration in the second limit velocity as the velocity of the initial impact is increased. This reduction appears to be linear up to about 85% of the V_{BL} . In this region the degradation is observed to fall in accordance with the equation,

$$V_2 = V_{BL} - 0.53V_1$$

For a V_1 above 85% of the V_{BL} , the deterioration is more rapid. If we compare the limit-boundary with that of an ideally plastic material (cf. Fig. 1c), we observe that the initial region ($V_1 < 0.85V_{BL}$) falls below this curve, while the latter region ($V_1 > 0.85V_{BL}$) matches quite closely. Plastic deformation is seen at all initial impact velocities, and the consequential thinning of the plate has a significant effect on the residual capacity to resist an impact.

4.1.2 Carbon fibre specimens

A markedly different limit-boundary is seen for the carbon fibre composite specimen. Here, virtually no deterioration in the limit velocity is seen in the region where $V_1 < 0.7V_{BL}$. Beyond this region there is a sharp drop-off in the strength of the composite with further increases in V_1 . The following expressions define the boundary-limit,

$$\begin{aligned} V_2 &= V_{BL} & \text{for } V_1 \leq 0.7V_{BL} \\ V_2 &= V_{BL} - 2V_1 & \text{for } V_1 > 0.7V_{BL} \end{aligned}$$

Comparing the composite with the idealised elastic material limit-boundary shows the composite to be close to this ideal before the onset of damage. When damage does occur in the composite, this is significantly more detrimental to the ballistic performance than that seen in the stainless steel. Damage mechanisms such as delamination and fibre breakage impair the structural integrity significantly compared with the more benign plastic dissipation mechanism seen in the stainless steel.

$$\bar{V}_{2BL} = \frac{V_{2BL}}{V_{BL}}$$

It should be noted that in all experiments for both materials and in the whole velocity range, the steel ball bearing projectiles showed no damage or plastic deformation.

4.2 Failure mechanisms

The stainless steel plates ultimately failed through plastic localisation in the plate leading to an initial rupture and tearing (Fig. 4a). The localisation, most obvious on the distal face, took the form of a ring measuring 10 mm in diameter (Fig. 4b). On the impacted face the fracture appears to be just inside of the region of contact between the surface of the ball bearing and the plate. This perhaps indicates a high degree of frictional contact between the ball and the plate.

The composite plate failed by fibre fracture. Observing the damage on the distal face, a cross shaped crack lying along the fibre directions resulted in the material being able to part, allowing passage of the projectile through the plate (Fig. 4c). On the impacted face a delaminated region is seen measuring about 30 mm across (Fig. 4d). Within this a second square-shaped region measuring about 9 mm across, defines the whole that allowed passage of the projectile. This hole is in fact small than the projectile diameter (12.7 mm) indicating significant ‘spring-back’ of the plate.

5 Conclusions

Stainless steel and carbon fibre/epoxy composite plates of equal mass were subjected to double-impact tests in order to assess their performance under multi-hit scenarios. The steel and composite plates showed a reasonable degree of agreement with the idealised limit-boundaries for the plastic and elastic materials respectively.

The steel plate, in absolute terms, outperformed the composite plate for all initial impact velocities, i.e. the limit-boundary of the composite plate lies completely within the locus or survival of the metallic plate. Thus the ballistic limit V_{BL} and the second ballistic limit V_{2BL} of the steel exceed that of the composite.

However, the ratio of these limits, which we shall denote as follows,

is a measure of the damage tolerance of the armour. For the stainless steel, this figure is 0.62, whilst for the carbon fibre composite it is 0.8.

Whilst in the present study, the composite system fared no better than the metal system despite its better damage tolerance, it may well be the case that under such circumstances where the number of impacts occurring at the same site is increased beyond 2, the composite will give a superior ballistic performance.

For circumstances such as these the parameter \bar{V}_{XBL} , where the subscript X indicates the number of equal impacts, could be defined. As the number of impacts increase, a composite system that sustains very little damage at low velocities may exhibit a threshold where by below a certain fraction of the ballistic limit, a system could sustain any number of impacts. The stainless steel results shows no indication that this limit would exist for a metallic system.

Fig.1. Illustrative plot of $V_1 - V_2$ space. (a) survival/failure points used to determine the (b) limit-boundary. (c) Idealised boundaries for

elastic and plastic materials. (d) Definition of the double equal velocity impact limit.

Fig.2. Experimental setup for the ballistic damage characterization: (a) front view of plate showing clamping arrangement, and (b) side view of the apparatus.

Fig.3. Maps showing the damage/residual penetration resistance of (a) stainless steel, and (b) carbon fibre/epoxy plates.

Fig.4. Plates on the point of rupture. (a) stainless steel plate (note the incipient crack) from the side and (b) the top showing more clearly the ring of localisation, and (c) carbon fibre composite plate where the projectile has lodged in the plate showing the cross shaped fracture that allows passage, and (d) the same plate view from the front.

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